

Synthesis of 1-Methyl-2-(2-hydrazino-4-thiazolyl)-benzimidazole and its Hydrazones

OM PRAKASH*, RAJESH K. TOMER and DHARMA R. KODALI

Department of Chemistry, Kurukshetra University, Kurukshetra-132 119

Manuscript received 18 August 1977, revised 9 March 1978, accepted 5 May 1978

1-Methyl-2-(2-hydrazino-4-thiazolyl)benzimidazole(II) and its eleven hydrazones(III) were synthesised by the condensation of 1-methyl-2-bromoacetylbenzimidazole(IV) with thiosemicarbazide and thiosemicarbazones respectively. 1-Methyl-2-bromoacetylbenzimidazole(IV) was prepared by the bromination of 1-methyl-2-acetylbenzimidazole(V) with bromine in dry chloroform. To confirm the structures(III), a compound (III, R=R'=CH₃) was synthesised by an alternative synthetic route in which II was reacted with acetone. All the final compounds II, III as well as intermediate (IV) were characterised by their i. r., nmr spectra and elemental analysis.

In view of significant anthelmintic activity in 2-[2-amino(or substituted amino)-4-thiazolyl]benzimidazoles (Ia) and their 1-alkyl derivatives¹⁻⁸ (Ib), it was considered of interest to synthesise 1-methyl-2-(2-hydrazino-4-thiazolyl)benzimidazole(II) and its hydrazones(III).

I
Ia, R = H,
Ib, R = alkyl.

In principle, compounds (III) belonging to this series could be prepared by two synthetic routes. Either II is prepared and then allowed to react with keto compounds or alternatively, thiosemicarbazones are condensed directly with 1-methyl-2-bromoacetylbenzimidazole(IV). The latter method was found to be convenient as II could be best obtained in only 45% yield and moreover somewhat difficult to purify. All the reaction sequences are given in scheme 1.

Scheme I

1-Methyl-2-bromoacetylbenzimidazole(IV) was prepared by the bromination of 1-methyl-2-acetylbenzimidazole(V) which in turn was prepared by the known method^{4,5}. Bromination of V was carried out successfully in dry chloroform at refluxing temperature and the structure of IV was confirmed by i.r. spectrum and its elemental analysis. Replace-

ment of a hydrogen atom of ($\text{—}\overset{\text{O}}{\parallel}\text{C—CH}_3$ group) by bromine resulted in expected shift of absorption frequency from 1675 cm^{-1} to 1690 cm^{-1} .

In order to confirm the structures of final compounds (III), a compound (III, R=CH₃, R'=CH₃) was prepared by employing both the synthetic routes. Both the compounds showed identical i.r. spectra and their mixed m.p. remained undepressed. The nmr spectrum of the compound displayed signals at δ 1.92 (s, 3H, CH₃); δ 2.08 (s, 3H, CH₃); δ 4.1 (s, 3H, N-CH₃); δ 7.1-8.0 (m, 4 aromatic proton, 1 thiazole, one NH proton). Other hydrazones were obtained by the condensation of IV with different aldehyde or ketone thiosemicarbazones and characterised by their i.r. spectra and elemental analysis. All the compounds (III) absorbed in the region of 3400-3200 cm^{-1} (NH stretching) and 1620-1600 cm^{-1} (NH bending) and did not show any absorption in the region of 1750-1650 cm^{-1} (absence of $>\text{C}=\text{O}$).

Experimental

All the melting points were taken in open capillaries in a sulphuric acid bath and are uncorrected. I.R. spectra were recorded on a Beckman IR-20 spectrophotometer. N.M.R. spectra were recorded on Perkin-Elmer 90 MHz spectrometer.

1-Methyl-2-bromoacetylbenzimidazole(IV) :

To a boiling solution of 1-methyl-2-acetylbenzi-

*Present Address : Chemistry Department, Meerut College, Meerut.

midazole (3.48 g, 0.02 mole) in dry chloroform (40 ml) was added a solution of bromine (3.2 g, 0.02 mole) in chloroform (10 ml), dropwise and with constant stirring. A light yellow solid began to separate after some time. After the addition was over, the reaction mixture was heated under reflux on a water bath for 1 hr. On cooling, hydrobromide was filtered off. IV.HBr m.p. 219-222° (decomp.) was suspended in water and neutralized with Na₂CO₃ solution, yielding 4.0 g (78%) of 1-methyl-2-bromoacetylbenzimidazole(IV) which was crystallized from aqueous ethanol (50%) m.p. 117-

O
||

119', I.R.(nujol) cm⁻¹, 1690 (—C—CH₂Br), Found : C, 47.20, H, 3.32, N, 10.86%. C₁₀H₉N₂OBr requires C, 47.43, H, 3.55, N, 11.06%.

1-Methyl-2-(2-hydrazino-4-thiazolyl)benzimidazole (II)

A solution of acetylthiosemicarbazide⁶ (1.33 g, 0.01 mole) in alcohol (40 ml) was added to a solution of IV(2.53 g, 0.01 mole) in alcohol (20 ml) and the mixture heated under reflux for 15-20 minutes. A yellow green solid which appeared in hot reaction mixture was hydrolysed by adding concentrated HCl

carbazone⁷ (2.23 g, 0.01 mole) in alcohol (20 ml) was added to a solution of IV(2.53 g, 0.01 mole) in alcohol (25 ml) and the mixture heated under reflux on a steam bath for 2 hr. On cooling a crystalline solid separated out, was filtered, washed with a little alcohol and treated with aqueous ammonia. The product was collected by filtration, washed with water and dried. It was crystallized from toluene, yield 75%, m.p. 140°, I.R. (nujol) cm⁻¹, 3320 (NH stretching) 1610 (NH bending), no absorption in the region 1650-1750 (>C=O absent). NMR (CDCl₃, δ); 2.24 (s, 3H, CH₃); 3.85 (s, 3H, OCH₃); 4.1 (s, 3H, N—CH₃); 6.8-8.0 (m, 8 aromatic protons, 1 thiazole and one NH proton). Found : C, 63.30, H, 5.32, N, 18.06%, C₂₀H₁₅N₅O₂S requires C, 63.66, H, 5.04, N, 18.57%.

Following the same method other compounds of this series were prepared. Their physical properties and analytical data are given in Table 1.

Acetone 4-[2-(1-methylbenzimidazolyl)]-2-thiazolylhydrazone(III, R=R'=CH₃) (Alternate method):

1-Methyl-2-(2-hydrazino-4-thiazolyl)benzimidazole (2.45 g, 0.01 mole) and acetone (50 ml) were

TABLE—1

Sl. No.	R	R'	M.P. °C	Yield %	Solvent of Cryst.	Molecular Formula	Found%			Required%		
							C	H	N	C	H	N
1.	CH ₃	CH ₃	184	76	A	C ₁₄ H ₁₆ N ₄ S	58.86	5.42	24.32	58.95	5.26	24.57
2.	H	C ₆ H ₅	242	70	C	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ N ₄ S	64.52	4.68	20.88	64.88	4.50	21.02
3.	CH ₃	C ₆ H ₅	220	65	B	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ N ₄ S	65.36	4.55	20.38	65.70	4.89	20.18
4.	CH ₃	<i>p</i> -OHC ₆ H ₄	182	68	A	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ N ₄ SO	62.51	4.42	19.08	62.81	4.68	19.29
5.	CH ₃	<i>p</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄	215	72	B	C ₁₉ H ₁₆ N ₄ SCl	59.80	4.56	18.48	59.75	4.19	18.35
6.	CH ₃	<i>p</i> -CH ₂ OC ₆ H ₄	140	75	A	C ₂₀ H ₁₉ N ₄ OS	63.90	5.32	18.06	63.66	5.04	18.57
7.	CH ₃	<i>p</i> -NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	221	80	B	C ₁₉ H ₁₆ N ₄ OS	58.42	4.46	21.24	58.16	4.08	21.43
8.	CH ₃	<i>p</i> -NH ₂ C ₆ H ₄	145	78	A	C ₁₉ H ₁₈ N ₄ S	62.56	4.64	23.46	62.98	4.97	23.20
9.	H	<i>2</i> -OCH ₃ -5-OHC ₆ H ₃	218	62	B	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ N ₄ O ₂ S	60.32	4.12	18.26	60.16	4.48	18.47
10.	H	<i>p</i> -(H ₃ C) ₂ NC ₆ H ₄	180	68	A	C ₂₀ H ₂₀ N ₄ S	63.52	5.56	22.52	63.83	5.32	22.34
11.	H	<i>p</i> -(H ₃ C) ₂ NC ₆ H ₄	175	74	A	C ₂₂ H ₂₄ N ₄ S	65.07	5.83	20.54	65.34	5.94	20.79

A=Toluene; B=Xylene; C=Dioxane/water.

(2 c.c.) and heating the reaction mixture under reflux for 1 hr afterwards. On cooling, a green solid separated out, which was collected by filtration, washed with little alcohol and treated with aqueous ammonia. The product was filtered off, washed with water and dried. It was crystallized from toluene m.p. 212° (decomp.) yield (45%), I.R.(nujol) cm⁻¹. 3410, 3200, 3100 (NH stretching), 1590 (NH bending). Found : C, 53.50%, H, 4.32, N, 28.35, C₁₁H₁₁N₂S requires C, 53.88, H, 4.49, N, 28.57%.

p-Methoxyacetophenone-4-[2-(1-methylbenzimidazolyl)]-2-thiazolylhydrazone(III, R=CH₃, R'=*p*-CH₃-OC₆H₄):

A solution of *p*-methoxyacetophenone thiosemi-

refluxed on a water bath for 4 hr. Excess of acetone was removed by distillation and the residual product was treated with water, dried and crystallized from toluene, m.p. and mixed m.p. 184°. Other data of the compound are given in Table 1.

Acknowledgement

We are thankful to Dr. S. N. Sawhney and Dr. S. P. Singh for their valuable guidance, to the Head of the Chemistry Department, Kurukshetra University, Kurukshetra for providing necessary facilities. The authors are also grateful to CSIR for the award of fellowships to us.

PRAKASH, TOMER & KODALI : SYNTHESIS OF 1-METHYL-2-(2-HYDRAZINO-4-THIAZOLYL), ETC.

References

1. Y. TASHIKA and K. TAKANASHI, *Japan Patent*, 1963, 20, 220(66) ; *Chem. Abs.*, 1967, 65, 65472n.
2. R. ARIES, *Belo. Patent*, 1966, 666, 351 ; *Chem. Abs.*, 1966, 64, 5465f.
3. CHIMETRON, *Fr. Patent*, 1966, 1,438,566; *Chem. Abs.*, 1966, 65, 20136d.
4. W. OZEGOWSKI and D. KREBS, *J. Prakt. Chem.*, 1965, 29, 18.
5. G. W. H. CHESSEMAN, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1964, 4645.
6. H. BEYER, H. HOHN and W. LASSIG, *Chem. Ber.*, 1952, 85, 1077 ; *Chem. Abs.*, 1953, 47, 11183h.
7. "Organic Compounds of Bivalent Sulphur", edited by E. E. REID, Chemical Publishing Co. Inc. (N.Y.), 1964, Vol. V, p. 201.